

Supplementary material:

Significance of climate indices to benthic conditions across the northern North Atlantic and adjacent shelf seas

Figure S1. Plot comparing cut-off weightings for the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) composites shown in Figure 5: (a) bottom salinity weights, and (b) bottom potential temperature weights. Contours show the point where the mean weighting for both the high and low years exceed the threshold value.

Figure S2. Plot comparing cut-off weightings for the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) composites shown in Figure 7: (a) bottom salinity weights, and (b) bottom potential temperature weights derived using the EN4 AMOC time-series; (c) bottom salinity weights, and (d) bottom potential temperature weights using the de-trended 1959-2009 Viking20 AMOC time-series. Contours show the point where the mean weighting for both the high and low years exceed the threshold value.

Figure S3. Plot comparing cut-off weightings for the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO) composites shown in Figure 8: (a) bottom salinity weights, and (b) bottom potential temperature weights. Contours show the point where the mean weighting for both the high and low years exceed the threshold value.

Figure S4. Plot comparing cut-off weightings for the Subpolar Gyre (SPG) composites shown in Figure 9: (a) bottom salinity weights, and (b) bottom potential temperature weights. Contours show the point where the mean weighting for both the high and low years exceed the threshold value.

Figure S5. Time-series for Case Study 1 (LoVe Observatory): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S6. Time-series for Case Study 2 (Western Scottish Slope): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\text{x } 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S7. Time-series for Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S8. Time-series for Case Study 4 (Mingulay Reef): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}C$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\times 10^{-2} m^2 s^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S9. Time-series for Case Study 5 (Porcupine Sea Bight): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\text{x } 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S10. Time-series for Case Study 6 (Bay of Biscay): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\text{x } 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S11. Time-series for Case Study 7 (Gulf of Cadiz / Alboran Sea): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\text{x } 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S12. Time-series for Case Study 8 (Azores): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\text{x } 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S13. Time-series for Case Study 9 (Reykjanes Ridge): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\text{x } 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S14. Time-series for Case Study 10 (Davis Strait): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S15. Time-series for Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S16. Time-series for Case Study 12 (USA mid-Atlantic Canyons): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S17. Time-series for Case Study 13 (European Slope): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.

Figure S18. Time-series for Case Study 14 (North Sea): (a) bottom potential temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) from EN4, (b) bottom salinity from EN4, and (c) bottom kinetic energy ($\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from Viking20. Colours in (a) and (b) show the EN4 data weighting variable ranging from 0-1, where 0 indicates the absence of observations and reversion to climatology, and 1 data-rich periods.